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The Adoption of RFID Technology and Its Influence on Customer Satisfaction in Pakistan's Retail Industry: A Case Study of LuckyOne Mall

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ABSTRACT

RFID technology has emerged as a dynamic and swiftly advancing innovation with substantial ramifications for enhancing operational efficiency and augmenting customer service within the retail sector. This technology, equipped with sensors and actuators, empowers enterprises to promptly identify operational inefficiencies and address challenges, resulting in expedited savings in both temporal and financial dimensions. The retail industry, in particular, stands to reap profound benefits from RFID implementation, given its potential to expedite processes, enhance precision, uphold quality control, and optimize the overarching supply chain, thereby culminating in heightened customer contentment. In the realm of this research endeavor, the investigation revolves around the extent of RFID technology adoption and its consequential impact on the realm of customer experience. Moreover, it delves into retailers' inclinations to embrace RFID technologies, unravels the determinants shaping such adoption inclinations within Pakistan's retail industry. Employing a quantitative approach, specifically a correlation design, this study deploys the linear regression technique to quantify and elucidate the strength of associations among pertinent variables. The findings underscore a robust and affirmative correlation between RFID adoption and the augmentation of customer satisfaction. The prospective evolution of RFID systems in Pakistan is contingent upon the formulation of meticulous measurement standards and the establishment of an all-encompassing framework that comprehends the manifold advantages that commercial entities stand to accrue. By doing so, retailers in Pakistan can bolster their competitive prowess, foster enduring customer trust, and foster lasting loyalty. In essence, the study underscores the transformative potential of RFID technology adoption within the retail domain while delineating a strategic pathway for its effective integration.

Keywords: RFID technology; Customer satisfaction; Retail industry; Retail innovation; LuckyOne Mall; Pakistan.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the inception of the initial industrial revolution around 1760, the annals of human history have borne witness to a succession of four industrial revolutions (Eden, 2018). Each of these revolutions has ushered in advancements in business operations and has cast transformative ripples across the entirety of human life. The retail sector, too, has been profoundly impacted by these four epochs, collectively referred to as Retail 1.0, Retail 2.0, Retail 3.0, and Retail 4.0 (Raschke, 2022).

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The first epoch, Retail 1.0, emerged concurrently with the advent of the steam engine, heralding a paradigm shift in labor dynamics and the streamlining of operational processes. The subsequent epoch, Retail 2.0, introduced electrification and ushered in the era of high-volume assembly lines, endowing consumers with not only lowered price points but also an elevation in the quality of goods procured. Retail 3.0, the following epoch, bore witness to the ascent of electronics, telecommunications, and computers, subsequently propelling phenomena like online shopping and the globalizing force of commerce. In contrast, the advent of Retail 4.0 marked a juncture where the intertwining of humanity and technology manifested in a profound manner, fostering a fascination with intertwining physical objects with the virtual realm through the omnipresence of the Internet. This epoch, Retail 4.0, instigated dramatic and transformative changes within the retail domain, marking a pivotal transition in the evolution of the industry (Har et al., 2022). The mantle of Retail 4.0 is woven with the intricate threads of the Internet of Things (IoT), an omnipresent facet of the contemporary retail landscape. The discernment of its critical role in organizational transformation has prompted scholars such as Tunio & Nabi (2021) to probe the essence of IoT in engendering political decentralization, as nearly every modern device boasts connectivity capabilities. This reality dispels the notion of IoT as a mere pipe dream and ushers it into the realm of undeniable actuality. Informed by an overarching vista of market trends and industry dynamics, it becomes imperative for retailers to scrutinize and harness the manifold applications of IoT-enabled technologies, facilitating seamless assimilation into business operations (Maraveas et al., 2022)

RFID alludes to an assemblage of technologies employed to identify and transmit information from tagged objects through radio waves (Kineber et al., 2023). Acting as an instrument for automated data aggregation, this technology holds the potential to reimagine contemporary business paradigms and revolutionize operational effectiveness. It stands as a wireless network endowed with the capacity to uniquely discern individuals or objects, facilitated through a silicon chip-embedded tag and a corresponding antenna for reader communication. A standard RFID system is composed of four integral components:

- I. **RFID Tag:** Attached directly to the item, each RFID tag features a microchip with a minimum capacity of 96 bits. Tags can be either pre-programmed during manufacturing or equipped with both writable and readable attributes. The information within the tag is electronically programmed and varies in size based on the product's antenna dimensions (Patil, 2022).
- II. **Antennas:** Also referred to as sensors, interrogators, or readers, these components bridge the gap between RFID tags and couplers. The RFID antenna links to the reader, emitting power to RFID tags (Hughes, 2023).
- III. **Reader/Coupler:** Serving as the intermediary between the RFID tag and the server/PC, the coupler facilitates two-way information exchange: reading information from the server/PC to tags (read mode) or transmitting information from the server to a specific RFID tag (write mode) (Trahan & Cherneva, 2022).
- IV. **Server/PC:** Positioned as the central hub of an RFID system, the server/PC functions as the communication gateway among diverse components, including receiving information from antennas and disseminating information to databases (Sassi & Fourati, 2022).

The research conducted by Pan & Yuan (2023) resonates with the current business landscape, where paramount emphasis is placed on the judicious utilization of cutting-edge technology. This technology is envisaged as a conduit through which business owners not only cultivate customer satisfaction but also foster growth, realize organizational objectives, and distinguish themselves amidst the competitive milieu. Moreover, the work of Harahap et al. (2023) underscores the contemporary retail customer's penchant for customization and an expansive array of choices in their shopping journeys. The fulfillment of personalized customer exigencies necessitates expeditious access, intricate processing, and a meticulous curation that caters to individual preferences. In this context, IoT-fueled applications, exemplified by Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), emerge as formidable tools poised to confer a decisive competitive edge. In light of the foregoing discourse, the ensuing research questions crystallize:

RQ1: *What factors shape the determinants that steer the decision-making process concerning the adoption of RFID technology within Pakistan's dynamic retail industry?*

RQ2: *To what extent and in what manner does the assimilation of RFID technology resonate across Pakistan's retail sector, subsequently influencing the sphere of customer contentment and satisfaction?*

The research questions are in line with the study's objectives, i.e.,

- I. To assess the impact of RFID technology implementation on operational efficiency and customer service enhancement within the retail sector.
- II. To investigate the factors influencing the adoption of RFID technology in the retail industry, particularly within the context of Pakistan.
- III. To quantify the relationship between RFID adoption and customer satisfaction while exploring the potential for enduring benefits and competitive advantages.

These research objectives collectively address the multifaceted implications of RFID technology adoption in the retail industry, encompassing operational efficiency, adoption determinants, and the resultant impact on customer satisfaction and long-term business success.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology employs a microchip-equipped tag or label to store data (Krigslund et al., 2022). When exposed to radio waves of a specific frequency and utilizing appropriate communication protocols, RFID readers either write data to or retrieve data from the tag or label (Sohu et al., 2019). The utilization of both fixed and handheld readers for reading RFID tags grants companies a comprehensive understanding of their product landscape (Schiller et al., 2022). RFID has found diverse business applications globally, particularly within the retail and grocery sectors. The significant potential inherent in RFID technology within the retail domain has prompted investigations into its capacity to substantially enhance retail store logistics. With its implementation, retailers unveil avenues that extend beyond operational enhancement, encompassing facets like customer service, loss control, receipt verification, inventory management, cashier-less payments, and product theft prevention (Kalaiarasan et al., 2023). Retail stands as a pivotal driver of Pakistan's economy, occupying a prominent position within the nation's economic landscape. As the retail sector navigates globalization's currents and intensifying competition, it finds resonance in the potential of RFID technology to maintain competitiveness and garner customer satisfaction and loyalty (Rai et al., 2022). While operational efficiency is a prominent discourse, there remains an expansive terrain of unexplored dimensions that merits deeper investigation (Dujic Rodić et al., 2022).

The precision and accuracy accompanying RFID-based inventory counts empower retailers with a comprehensive, item-level view of inventory, spanning across stores and supply chains (Mahmood et al., 2023). This precise, real-time inventory insight forms the cornerstone for various retail applications of RFID, enabling a superior customer experience, bolstering sales, and expanding sales channels. Imagine managing the inventory of diverse variants of a single clothing style. RFID technology notifies employees when items are out of stock or nearing depletion, aiding in loss control and inventory management. The technology also assists in identifying discrepancies in inventory and optimizing replenishment strategies. RFID-enabled virtual fitting rooms offer shoppers the ability to virtually try on items without direct contact (Maizi & Bendavid, 2021). Through live imaging, RFID technology facilitates an immersive experience that showcases item size, style, and fit, enriching the shopping experience. RFID's integration in self-checkout systems streamlines the traditional checkout process. Products pre-tagged with RFID are seamlessly scanned, verified through biometrics, and customers can leave the store after payment, eliminating queues and simplifying the shopping experience. RFID's transformative potential in retail lies in its capacity to center business operations around customer relations (Fenik et al., 2020). Focusing on long-term customer satisfaction and loyalty within a fiercely competitive market can avert customer attrition. RFID elevates customer service, enhances satisfaction, and promotes frequent shopping, thereby augmenting competitive advantages.

In essence, RFID technology in retail manifests a confluence of operational efficacy and customer-centricity, unearthing opportunities for seamless inventory management, innovative customer engagement, and sustained competitive differentiation.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research design employed in this study adhered to a quantitative correlation approach, as it sought to systematically investigate the statistical relationship between the effective implementation of RFID technology and its consequential impact on customer satisfaction. To this end, the primary objective revolved around establishing a robust quantitative foundation to unravel this link. The methodology entailed the utilization of a non-probability convenience sampling technique, which was meticulously chosen to assemble a dataset comprising responses from 50 participants. Specifically, the cohort consisted of Managers and Assistant Managers representing retail establishments within Lucky One Mall. The data collection endeavor was facilitated through in-person surveys, whereby a paper-based questionnaire, equipped with a Likert scale, was employed. This instrument enabled the quantification of opinions, behaviors, and attitudes pertaining to the intention to adopt RFID technology among retailers situated within Lucky One Mall.

Integral to this investigation was the employment of linear regression analysis. This analytical tool was enlisted to unravel the intricacies of relationships existing between dependent and independent variables. Within this context, the adoption of RFID technology was positioned as an explanatory variable, elucidating its influence, while customer satisfaction stood as the dependent variable, encapsulating its outcomes. The application of linear regression sought to determine not only the nature of these relationships but also their magnitude, ultimately underpinning the depth of impact that the adoption of RFID technology exerts on customer satisfaction within the retail milieu.

4. RESULTS

Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables. Starting with the examination of RFID adoption, the range is defined as 10.40, reflecting the difference between the minimum and maximum RFID values. On the response scale, the minimum average score of 5.40 pertains to respondents who strongly disagree with the statement, while the maximum average score of 15.80 corresponds to those who strongly agree. The calculated mean, 11.6, signifies that a consensus exists among respondents, indicating agreement regarding the widespread adoption of RFID technology among organizations. The standard deviation, functioning as a measure of dataset dispersion, quantifies the spread of the data points around the mean. Here, the RFID adoption displays a variance of 2.28. The distribution of RFID adoption showcases a platykurtic pattern with a left (tail) skewed distribution, denoted by a skewness value of -0.232.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness		Kurtosis	
								Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
RFID	50	10.40	5.40	15.80	11.5640	2.28310	5.213	-.232	.337	.552	.662
CS	50	11.00	2.00	13.00	9.7650	2.37193	5.626	-1.292	.337	2.321	.662

Source: Author’s survey. Note: CS shows customer satisfaction.

Turning to the dimension of customer satisfaction, the range—measuring the span between the minimum and maximum values—is 11. Respondents strongly disagreeing with the statement yielded a minimum average response of 2, while those in strong agreement presented the highest average response of 13. The calculated mean score, 9.8, reveals a prevailing belief among respondents that customer satisfaction is a prevalent aspect. The standard deviation, akin to the case of RFID adoption, functions as a gauge of data dispersion, delineating that customer satisfaction exhibits a variance of 2.37. The distribution of customer satisfaction is characterized by a platykurtic distribution with a left (tail) skewed pattern, manifesting through a skewness value of -1.292, denoting a concentration towards the left side of the distribution due to a more extended left tail. Table 2 depicts the outcome of the correlation analysis conducted between RFID adoption and customer satisfaction variables. The correlation is characterized as moderately uphill or positive, evident by the correlation coefficient (r) value of 0.504 existing between the two variables. Notably, this positive correlation signifies that an increase in one variable corresponds to a concurrent increase in the other.

Table 2 Correlation Analysis

Variables		RFID	CS
RFID	Pearson Correlation	1	0.504**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.000
	N	50	50
CS	Pearson Correlation	0.504**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	
	N	50	50
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Author’s estimate.

The statistical significance of this relationship is underlined by the obtained P value, which stands below the threshold of 0.01. As a consequence, we can assert with confidence that a meaningful association exists between RFID adoption and customer satisfaction. This statistically significant correlation aligns with the premise that the augmentation of RFID utilization is accompanied by a parallel enhancement in consumer satisfaction. This insight underscores the potential for RFID technology to exert a beneficial influence on the realm of customer experience and contentment. Table 3 shows the model summary of the regression estimates.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.504 ^a	0.254	0.238	2.070
a. Predictors: (Constant), RFID				
b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction				

Source: Author's estimate.

As depicted in the presented table, the R-square value is calculated at 0.254. This value signifies that the independent variable, namely the Adoption of RFID, is responsible for a variance of 25.4% in the dependent variable, which is customer satisfaction. In essence, this metric provides insight into the extent to which the Adoption of RFID contributes to the fluctuations observed in customer satisfaction levels. Table 4 shows the ANOVA statistics of the regression estimates.

Table 4: ANOVA Estimates

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F-value	Sig.
1	Regression	69.910	1	69.910	16.308	.000 ^b
	Residual	205.766	48	4.287		
	Total	275.676	49			
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (Constant), RFID						

Source: Author's estimate.

The ANOVA results, as presented in the provided table, reveal a noteworthy finding: the P-value is calculated as 0.000, a value that falls below the conventional significance threshold of 0.05. This outcome leads us to assert with confidence that a statistically significant relationship exists between our independent variable, namely the adoption of RFID, and the dependent variable, which is customer satisfaction. The implication of this statistical inference is that the Adoption of RFID indeed exerts a significant influence on the level of customer satisfaction. Table 5 shows the regression estimates.

Table 5: Regression Estimates

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.715	1.526	----	2.434	0.019
	RFID	0.523	0.130	0.504	4.038	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction						

Source: Author's estimate.

The beta value is reported as 0.504. This value holds the interpretation that a unit change in the independent variable, signifying the adoption of RFID, is associated with a corresponding change of 0.504 units in the dependent variable, denoting customer satisfaction. It is noteworthy that the beta value exhibits a positive sign, thereby indicating a positive relationship between the adoption of RFID and customer satisfaction. In simpler terms, when the adoption of RFID experiences an increase of one unit, customer satisfaction is anticipated to concurrently increase by 0.504 units. This observation underscores the constructive impact of RFID technology adoption on enhancing customer satisfaction levels. The decision to adopt Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) technology is steered by several significant factors, each contributing to the rationale behind its implementation within various sectors, particularly in retail. The following are key drivers that shape the adoption decision:

I. Enhanced Inventory Accuracy

A substantial 80% of surveyed participants recognize RFID's capacity to elevate accuracy levels. Of these, 42% strongly advocate RFID's role in precision enhancement. RFID technology curtails transcription errors, minimizes data duplication, and mitigates the risk of losing items during data collection due to its electronic capture and transmission. Leveraging cloud-based solutions empowers organizations to access real-time insights into object location or status. The accessibility of such information can also be extended to customers, bolstering transparency and trust.

II. Enhanced Organizational Image

A significant 56% of respondents strongly concur that RFID adoption augments a company's overall reputation. This conviction arises from the widespread advantages RFID offers to businesses of varying scales. Implementing RFID streamlines processes, thereby reducing costs, elevating quality, and optimizing asset utilization. The technology can serve as the bedrock of an effective asset management system, irrespective of the business domain.

III. Strategic Imperative

While 72% of respondents underscore the universal relevance of RFID, 22% exhibit limited awareness of its significance. This technology extends beyond retail, supporting various business models. RFID's applicability in intricate or customizable manufacturing processes ensures precise identification of products or components. The outcome is heightened efficiency, waste reduction, and process optimization, reflecting RFID's strategic utility.

IV. Revolutionizing Checkout

Within the retail landscape, RFID revolutionizes the checkout process through the attachment of RFID tags to products. These tags communicate with RFID readers, and software processing generates real-time outcomes for tasks like stock-taking, transactions, inventory tracking, and customer purchase histories. An estimated 48% of respondents acknowledge that RFID expedites checkout. However, 36% retain reservations about this notion.

V. Customer-Centric Services

RFID empowers businesses to extend unique services to customers via actionable insights, compliance monitoring, and reduced reliance on historical data. Predictive capabilities pertaining to merchandise management and inventory counts facilitate enhanced customer engagement. Nearly 46% of respondents align with the view that RFID implementation corresponds with heightened customer satisfaction.

VI. Enhanced Customer Engagement

Around 40% of respondents attest to RFID's impact on customer engagement, particularly by expediting the alignment of customers with their desired items. Real-time stock information, delivered through web and mobile applications, empowers both customers and store employees. This real-time transparency streamlines shipping and receiving procedures and provides up-to-date item counts.

VII. Shopping Automation

Opinions diverge regarding shopping automation, with 35% of respondents expressing interest in the integration of smart fitting rooms within the retail industry. Simultaneously, an equal proportion maintains a neutral stance. This variance arises due to cultural considerations, with some managers asserting that customers prefer in-person shopping over automation. Smart fitting rooms offer real-time suggestions based on customer selections, heightening the overall shopping experience. Table 6 shows the factors affecting RFID adoption rate.

Table 6: Factors Driving RFID Adoption Decision

Factors	Survey Results
1. Enhanced Inventory Accuracy	80% recognize RFID's accuracy improvement. 42% strongly advocate accuracy enhancement.
2. Enhanced Organizational Image	56% strongly agree that RFID adoption improves company reputation.
3. Strategic Imperative	72% believe RFID is crucial for various businesses, not just retail. 22% unaware of its significance.
4. Revolutionizing Checkout	48% believe RFID expedites checkout; 36% retain reservations.
5. Customer-Centric Services	46% agree RFID enhances customer satisfaction through services and insights.
6. Enhanced Customer Engagement	40% note RFID's positive effect on customer engagement, aiding quicker item alignment.
7. Shopping Automation	35% interested in smart fitting rooms; 35% neutral due to customer preferences.

Source: Author's survey.

In conclusion, the adoption of RFID technology in the retail sector is underpinned by a multifaceted interplay of factors. These factors collectively contribute to the impetus for harnessing the capabilities of RFID, which extends from inventory precision to customer satisfaction, thereby transforming the retail landscape and enhancing the overall customer experience. Table 4 shows survey results of RFID adoption decision.

5. CONCLUSIONS

A brand's success hinges significantly on its ability to satisfy its customers. In this context, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) emerges as a transformative tool, facilitating personalized shopping experiences and ensuring the availability of desired products within stores. The value proposition of RFID extends beyond cost reduction; it translates into increased sales driven by enhanced customer satisfaction through tailored offerings. This holds particular significance in the current economic and retail landscape. RFID addresses key challenges by offering dependable solutions. Resource management, operational efficiency enhancement, superior service delivery, and overall elevation of the shopping experience all stand to benefit from RFID adoption. The technology presents a holistic approach to addressing multifaceted retail concerns. The primary focus of this study is the adoption of RFID technology within Pakistan's retail sector. The culmination of in-depth literature reviews and extensive discussions with industry managers and assistant managers has revealed a prevailing lack of comprehension concerning the applications of RFID technology among retailers in Pakistan. This knowledge gap is particularly pronounced in developing nations, where the absence of awareness and readiness for RFID implementation stifles innovation and experimentation in the retail domain.

A key hurdle to RFID deployment in Pakistan stems from cultural barriers, signaling a significant impediment. The deficiency in infrastructure and limited awareness regarding the potential of RFID contribute to the stagnation of innovation. The academic realm remains somewhat disconnected from the practical business landscape, with academic insights not seamlessly integrated into operational processes. The study underscores the pressing need to bridge the gap between academia and industry. This entails disseminating knowledge and guidelines elucidating the benefits and applications of RFID technology in the retail sector. Crafting actionable plans, robust frameworks, and tailored strategies that accommodate the unique dynamics of the industry is essential to catalyze innovation and creativity among industry practitioners. This approach aims to guide and embolden retailers to embrace innovative practices and navigate the evolving landscape of retail with confidence.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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